

EXPERIENCES AND CONCEPTS ON IMPROVING THE COLLABORATIVE COMPETENCE OF FAMILY AND WOMEN'S SYSTEM EMPLOYEES IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Abstract. *This article is about experiences and concepts on improving the collaborative competence of family and women's system. Decisive importance in ensuring the effectiveness of the reforms implemented in the field of professionalism of the employees of the Family and Women's System. Also, social and pedagogical improvement of collaboration competences of workers of a system of family and women.*

Keywords: *experiences, concepts, social support, family, women's, professionalism, collaborative competencies, protection, educate talented, interests of women, gender equality.*

Equality between women and men in the world of work has seen some encouraging improvements, but progress on closing gender gaps has stalled.³ Persistent disparities remain between women and men, including in labour market participation, pay for work of equal value, representation of women in high-paying occupations and managerial positions, and the distribution of unpaid care work. Violence and harassment, including sexual harassment, also remains a reality for many women in the world of work. Achieving economic empowerment and gender equality for women will require proactive and transformative policies from a variety of global stakeholders, including governments, companies, employers' and workers' organizations, and civil society.

Promote education, training and professional development for women:

Invest in workplace policies and programmes that open avenues for advancement of women at all levels and across all business areas, and encourage women to enter nontraditional job fields.

Ensure equal access to all company-supported education and training programmes, including literacy classes, vocational and information technology training.

Provide equal opportunities for formal and informal networking and mentoring.

Articulate the company's business case for women's empowerment and the positive impact of inclusion for men as well as women.

Today, in our Republic, protection of the rights and legal interests of women, increasing their economic, social and political activity, maintaining their health, providing vocational training and employment, wide involvement in entrepreneurship, social support of needy women "support, reforms to ensure gender equality are being carried out systematically. Their collaborative competencies are of great importance in increasing the role of women in society, bringing the professionalism and efficiency of the family and women's system employees to the international level as a system responsible for gender equality and family issues.

The National Program on Increasing the Activity of Women in All Aspects of the Economic, Political and Social Life of the Country in 2022-2026, approved by the Decree of the

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.87 to further strengthen the protection system, to strengthen their health, to create the necessary conditions for the education of girls, to educate talented and educated girls and to increase their scientific potential, to improve the legal basis for protecting the rights and legal interests of women, to improve the social status of women - focused on important tasks such as increasing economic and political activity, strengthening their role in society, particularly in state administration, and ensuring gender equality. The President signed the decree "On measures to improve the system of working with families and women, supporting the neighborhood and religious people." The decree establishes the following: State Committee for Family and Women; Ministry of Makhalla and Support of Elderly people.

The committee is an authorized state management body for the development and implementation of a unified state policy in the field of family and women support, protection of their rights and legal interests.

The following were defined as the main tasks of the committee:

- protecting the rights and legal interests of women, increasing their role and activity in the social and political life of the country, ensuring gender equality guarantees, wide involvement in scientific activities;
- timely identification of family and women's problems, provision of socio-legal and psychological assistance to families and women in a difficult social situation;
- creating the necessary conditions for women to acquire knowledge and skills in occupations that are in high demand in the labor market, widely involving women in rural areas in family and private entrepreneurship, handicrafts;
- implementation of targeted measures on formation of a healthy lifestyle among women, strengthening of spiritual and moral values in the family;

The Important and purpose of the study is to develop the content, principles and mechanism of improving the collaborative competence of family and women's system employees by means of a performative approach, relying on the priority principles of social pedagogy.

Collaborative competence is considered one of the important competencies of family and women's system employees. Collaborative competence expresses the following characteristics: cooperation, goal-oriented team activity, specific activity focused on efficiency, self- and mutual assessment, intensive exchange of information. Collaborative competence can be defined as a person's ability to engage in active activities in society.

Collaborative competence or working in a team in cooperation is one of the necessary characteristics of representatives of the social sphere. The application of the performative approach in organizing one's activities on the basis of important principles such as mutual trust, honesty, "unity of word and deed" has a practical nature. Collaborative competence helps employees of the family and women's system to create new solutions, ideas and concepts to problems, to form and implement social projects.

Performative language' considers issues concerning the meaning and effects of language, identity and the nature of the subject. Performative utterances do not describe but perform the action they designate. Theorists have long asserted that we must attend to what literary language does as much as to what it says, and the concept of the performative provides a linguistic and philosophical justification for this idea. The performative brings to Centre stage an active, world-making use of language, which resembles literary language — and helps us to conceive of

literature as act or event. The work of Austin and Derrida develops the theory of performativity and Butler applies it to gender.

In the performative approach, the advantage of improving the activities of specialists in the family and women's systems is that the words and concepts used in communication, based on the activities to be performed, are organized in a clear, purposeful and stable manner. A performative approach is one that involves the act of directing, performing, prescribing, or attempting to accomplish something by saying something. The important rules of the performative approach are as follows: it should be implemented by responsible persons, the content should be clear, and there should be specific conditions and systems for the implementation of the activity based on this content.

Performative writing is not so much a matter of style and form as a discursive, rhetorical practice. It presents textual moments that invoke performance and is grounded in the corporality of the body, calling attention to physical bodies in relation and movement. Because performative writing contains a rhetoric of potential action, it can have real social and political consequences. It stages a particular type of encounter between textuality and social realities, a relationship that appears in each of the primary texts I explore in this project. The work of these women is an active response to and reworking of social and political issues, and it acknowledges the complex relationship between history/politics and art/aesthetic form. I understand this labor as a modernist performance; I do not attempt to define or demonstrate the most illustrative examples of performative writing; nor do I aim to lay out a conclusive and complete definition. Rather, I am interested in discovering how performative writing acts in the world and what effects it has. I lead with the writers themselves and map several trajectories of performative writing through these writers and their work. I chose these writers because they employ similar rhetorical strategies and have shared stylistic practices.

A performative approach differs from performing an action by saying a sentence and creating a sentence by performing it. This means that it is possible to act with the meaning of the statement by showing oneself by saying or acting on it. The professionalism of family and women's system employees is of decisive importance in ensuring the effectiveness of the reforms implemented in the field. On the other hand, family and women's system, like all areas, is considered as an important system in the processes of globalization.

Women are significantly under-represented in the STEM fields, which generate higher-paying jobs, such as software developers, mathematicians, engineers, IT managers and biochemists. It is here that the future of work is being shaped, with serious impacts on gender equality. Women are less likely to have digital skills, and the digital skills they do have generate lower returns than for their male counterparts. Between 2000 and 2016, women's representation in the top three IT occupations actually declined in the United States, especially in its largest tech hubs, despite gains in overall numbers of women, "making the field even more male-dominated than it used to be". In EU countries, women comprise only 17 per cent of people in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) studies and careers and only 36 per cent of STEM graduates, although girls outpace boys in digital literacy. Lifelong learning policies that encourage young women to expand their skills into STEM fields can also help prepare women to meet the challenges associated with the changing world of work.

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